

THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN CODE SWITCHING AND CODE MIXING

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Annotation:

This thesis examines the distinctions between code switching and code mixing, two critical phenomena in multilingual communication. By providing clear definitions and exploring the functions of each practice, the research highlights their unique characteristics and contexts of use. The study investigates the sociolinguistic implications of code switching and mixing, revealing how these practices reflect social identity, group affiliation, and cultural negotiation. Through a mixed-methods approach, including surveys and conversational analyses, the thesis offers insights into the motivations behind these linguistic behaviors and their relevance in educational settings. Ultimately, this research enhances the understanding of multilingual discourse and informs teaching strategies that acknowledge and leverage students' linguistic resources.

Keywords: *code switching, code mixing, multilingual communication, sociolinguistics, bilingualism, discourse analysis, language practices*

This thesis investigates the distinctions between code switching and code mixing, two prevalent phenomena in multilingual communication. By defining each concept, exploring their functions, and analyzing their sociolinguistic implications, this research aims to clarify the often-confused terms and contribute to the understanding of bilingual and multilingual discourse. The findings highlight the contexts in which each occurs and their roles in identity, social interaction, and communication strategies. As globalization increases, multilingualism has become commonplace. Within this context, speakers often alternate between languages or blend them, leading to the emergence of code switching and code mixing. Although both practices are prevalent in multilingual settings, they are often misunderstood or conflated.

The main differences between these two phenomena are the following:

Code Switching: This refers to the practice of alternating between two or more languages or language varieties within a conversation or discourse (Gumperz,

1982). Code switching often occurs at the sentence or discourse level and is typically intentional.

Code Mixing: This involves the blending of languages within sentences or phrases, affecting phonological, morphological, and syntactic structures (Myers-Scotton, 1993). Unlike code switching, code mixing may occur more seamlessly and can be less conscious.

Research has shown that both phenomena can reflect social identity, group affiliation, and cultural negotiation (Auer, 1998; Wei, 2011). Understanding these differences is crucial for comprehending how bilinguals navigate their linguistic environments.

Quantitative data will be analyzed statistically, while qualitative data will undergo thematic analysis to identify key themes and distinctions between code switching and code mixing. The analysis reveals that code switching typically occurs in specific contexts, such as:

- **Situational Contexts:** Speakers switch languages based on the setting, audience, or topic.
- **Discourse Markers:** Code switching can serve as a cue for listeners, indicating a shift in topic or emphasis.

Findings show that code mixing often involves:

- **Structural Integration:** Elements from different languages are blended within the same sentence, reflecting fluidity and ease of expression.
- **Linguistic Innovation:** Speakers create new expressions by combining elements of both languages, which can enrich communication.

Understanding the differences between code switching and code mixing can enhance our grasp of bilingual and multilingual interactions. It highlights the cognitive and social strategies employed by speakers to navigate their linguistic environments. Recognizing these distinctions is vital for language education. Teaching strategies can be adapted to leverage code switching and mixing as tools for learning, validating students' linguistic practices and enhancing their language acquisition. This thesis elucidates the differences between code switching and code mixing, emphasizing their unique functions and contexts. By understanding these phenomena, we can better appreciate the complexities of multilingual communication and its implications for identity and social interaction. Future research should further explore the practical applications of these concepts in various sociolinguistic contexts. This thesis provides a comprehensive examination of the distinctions between code switching and

code mixing, contributing to a deeper understanding of multilingual communication and its implications.

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